

Instructions for using DExplore's Docker version

To use DExplore from its Docker version, follow these steps:

1. Download and install Docker Desktop on your personal computer. Docker Desktop is a free application provided by Docker® and is compatible with Windows, Mac, and Linux operating systems. You can download it from <https://www.docker.com/products/docker-desktop/>.
2. Create a free account on Docker® to access Docker Hub. Docker Hub enables you to pull existing Docker images, such as DExplore, or push your own images.
3. After installing Docker Desktop and creating a Docker® account, you can pull the DExplore Docker image via Docker Desktop.

4. Running DExplore's Docker image is straightforward since Docker Desktop operates through a graphical user interface (GUI), eliminating the need for command-line inputs.

5. We strongly recommend users to configure optional settings as depicted in the following screenshot.

6. After configuring the settings, click the "Run" button. Open a new browser tab and enter "localhost:3838/dexplore/" in the address bar.
7. DExplore will run in the browser, mimicking its online version without any size restrictions or stability issues.

These steps ensure a smooth and user-friendly experience with DExplore's Docker version.

For troubleshooting, do not hesitate to contact us at [dexplore.app\[at\]gmail.com](mailto:dexplore.app[at]gmail.com).